

Short communication

First record of *Leucopis (Leucopis) spyrothecae* (Dip.: Chamaemyiidae) from Iran

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چکیده

طی نمونه‌برداری‌های انجام‌شده از دشمنان طبیعی شته‌ها در اردیبه‌ل طی سال‌های ۹۱-۱۳۹۰، لاروهای مگس شکارگر از خانواده Chamaemyiidae در حال تغذیه از شته *Pemphigus spyrothecae* Passerini روی درخت صنوبر، *Populus nigra* (L.) جمع‌آوری و پس از پرورش در شرایطی مشابه شرایط محل جمع‌آوری، حشرات کامل به نام *Leucopis (Leucopis) spyrothecae* Raspi, 2003 شناسایی شدند. این گونه برای اولین بار از ایران گزارش می‌شود.

The members of the dipteran family Chamaemyiidae are small, generally silvery grey flies (1-5 mm long), with black spots on the abdomen, found in all zoogeographical regions, although the majority of species are known from the Palaearctic region. Our overall knowledge about this family in the Palaearctic region is still poor, partly due to difficulties in collection and species determination, in particular with regard to females (Triplehorn & Johnson, 2005; Raspi & Ebejer, 2008; Gaimari, 2012). This family includes more than 140 species in the Palaearctic region and only a few species have already been recorded from Iran (Ghadiri Rad *et al.*, 1999, Rakhshani *et al.*, 2010).

During a survey on the natural enemies of aphids in Ardabil during 2012-13, chamaemyiid larvae were found feeding on the aphid *Pemphigus spyrothecae* Passerini on *Populus nigra* (L.). They were collected and reared in the same condition until the adults of *Leucopis (Leucopis) spyrothecae* Raspi, 2003 emerged in April 2012 and April 2013. This species is newly recorded from Iran.

The genus *Leucopis* Meigen is placed in the subfamily Leucopinae and distinguished from the genus *Lipoleucopis* de Meijere by its costal vein meeting vein M and usually lack of prescutellum (McClean, 1998). The species *L. (Leucopis) spyrothecae* can be separated from related species by the combination of following characters: mesonotum with weak, dark grey median stripes and shaded greyish-brown dorsocentral vittae; three pairs of posterior dorsocentral setae, anterior dorsocentral setae shorter than posterior ones; abdominal tergites III-V with dense stout setulae; distal half of aedeagus tapered; female sternite VI kidney-shaped, sternite VII with two symmetrical sclerites; tergite VII reduced with anteriorly narrow, transverse, weakly sclerotized band bending backwards laterally; spermatheca spherical, strongly sclerotized (fig. 1, A-F).

Material examined – 47 ♀♀, 29 ♂♂, IRAN: Ardabil province, N 38°19'32", E 48°25'28", 1315 m., 5.iii.2013, leg. M. Ghafouri Moghaddam.

Fig. 1. *Leucopis (Leucopis) spyrothecae*, female: (A) dorsal view, (B) terminalia in ventral view; male: (C) dorsal view of abdomen, (D) anterior paramere, (E) phallus, (F) genitalia.

Raspi (1995) misidentified *L. (Leucopis) spyrothecae* as *L. (Leucopis) steinbergi* Tanasijtshuk. The former species is also superficially similar to *Leucopis bursaria* (Rondani), except for the characteristic morphology of its mesonotum (Raspi, 2003).

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